

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CHARACTER CREATION METHODS IN EASTERN AND WESTERN LITERATURES

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Abstract. This article provides a comparative analysis of stylistic and aesthetic differences in character creation between Eastern and Western literatures. The research examines how authors' literary characters reflect attitudes toward society, humanity, and spirituality. The symbolism, philosophical nature, and spirituality characteristic of Eastern literature are compared with realistic, psychological, and individualistic approaches in Western literature. Similar and different aspects of character creation are revealed through cultural-historical factors, poetic traditions, and descriptive means.

Keywords: Eastern literature, Western literature, character creation, comparative analysis, aesthetic criteria, symbol, psychological analysis, cultural context.

Аннотация. В данной статье проводится сравнительный анализ стилистических и эстетических различий в создании образов в восточной и западной литературе. В исследовании рассматривается, как через литературные образы, созданные авторами, отражается отношение к обществу, человеку и духовности. Символизм, философичность и духовность, характерные для восточной литературы, сопоставляются с реалистическим, психологическим и индивидуалистическим подходами западной литературы. Выявляются сходства и различия в создании образов на основе культурно-исторических факторов, поэтических традиций и выразительных средств.

Ключевые слова: восточная литература, западная литература, создание образов, сравнительный анализ, эстетические критерии, символ, психологический анализ, культурный контекст.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Sharq va G'arb adabiyotlarida obraz yaratishning uslubiy va estetik farqlari qiyosiy tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda mualliflar tomonidan yaratilgan adabiy obrazlar orqali jamiyat, inson va ma'naviyatga bo'lgan munosabat qanday ifodalangani o'rganiladi. Sharq adabiyotiga xos timsoliylik, falsafiylik va ma'naviylik G'arb adabiyotidagi realistik, psixologik va individualistik yondashuvlar bilan solishtiriladi. Madaniy-tarixiy omillar, poetik an'analar va tasviriy vositalar asosida obraz yaratishdagi o'xshash va farqli jihatlar ochib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Sharq adabiyoti, G'arb adabiyoti, obraz yaratish, qiyosiy tahlil, estetik mezonlar, timsol, psixologik tahlil, madaniy kontekst.

Introduction: Literary characters form the aesthetic foundation of any national literature. Through them, authors express their attitudes toward social life, human destiny, and moral standards. Eastern and Western literatures have developed based on their own poetic traditions, stylistic approaches, and artistic methods, making the analysis of character creation features in these two literary schools one of the relevant directions in literary studies. In both literary traditions, characters are considered the main means of reflecting the reality of life, but there are

differences in the aesthetic criteria, metaphorical images, depth of psychological analysis, system of symbols, and authorial position used in their creation.

Literature Review: In Zhirmunsky's work, the philosophical content of symbols in Eastern literature is contrasted with the psychological depth in Western literature. Mareeva's views on cultural theory focus on the cultural roots of aesthetic approaches to character creation. Zhang Yan compares the descriptive methods in Eastern and Western art, revealing their expression in literature. Gutareva and Vinogradov analyze cultural differences, examining the mental differences in the formation of literary characters. These sources provide a theoretical and practical foundation for the article.

Zhirmunsky's *Selected Works. Comparative Literary Studies. East and West* deeply analyzes the main differences between Eastern and Western literatures, their artistic thinking, and methods of character creation. The author emphasizes that characters in Eastern literature are more often expressed through symbols with a higher spiritual-aesthetic approach, while realistic expression and psychological details prevail in Western literature. Through this approach, the difference in aesthetic criteria between the two literary schools is revealed.[1] The work demonstrates the specific methods of both regional literatures in descriptive means, plot construction, and character illumination, providing a thorough analysis of similarities and differences between them. Additionally, the researcher pays attention to the roots of differences in character creation, taking into account cultural-historical factors. These aspects directly correspond to the scientific direction of the topic "Comparative Analysis of Character Creation Methods in Eastern and Western Literatures."

Mareeva's textbook *Cultural Studies. Theory and History of Culture* broadly covers the theoretical foundations and historical development of culture, analyzing the interconnection of aesthetic views and artistic expression means formed within various civilizations. The author shows that approaches to character creation can be understood through the historical formation of Eastern and Western cultures, their mentality, value system, and attitude toward art. The work focuses on how expression styles in art and literature have developed through culture types, symbol systems, archetypes, and the formation of mythological images.[2] These ideas serve as a theoretical basis for comparative analysis of character creation methods in Eastern and Western literatures and help understand the influence of cultural context on artistic characters. In this respect, this source provides a suitable literary-historical foundation for the topic.

Zhang Yan's article *Chinese and Western Aesthetics: Theory of the Relationship Between Painting and Thinking* analyzes the main differences between Eastern and Western art and aesthetic thinking and their reflection in artistic expression. The author emphasizes that character creation in traditional Chinese art is more achieved through harmony with nature, inner spiritual state, and philosophical views, while Western art focuses on accurately reflecting external reality, visual details, and realism. These views are also reflected in literary character creation, as art and literature in both cultures are closely interconnected.[3] Zhang Yan compares the artistic thinking of the two civilizations through the aesthetic foundations, descriptive approaches, and means of expression in character creation. This article serves as a theoretical and aesthetic basis for the comparative study of character creation methods in Eastern and Western literatures, especially for understanding the relationship between artistic thinking and descriptive expression.

Gutareva and Vinogradov's article *Comparative Analysis of Eastern and Western Cultures* comparatively studies the cultural differences between the two civilizations, their historical formation, worldview, and aesthetic values. The authors emphasize that inner

harmony, loyalty to tradition, and symbolic thinking play a key role in Eastern culture, while individualism, rational thinking, and the primacy of external expression prevail in Western culture.[4] These differences are also reflected in artistic creation, particularly in character creation. The article shows that characters in Eastern literature are built more on a symbolic, philosophical, and conceptual basis, while Western literature emphasizes the psychological depth of characters and realistic depiction. These analyses provide an important theoretical basis for the comparative study of character creation methods in literature and serve as an important source for understanding the specific aspects of Eastern and Western literary thinking. This article strengthens the scientific foundations of the topic.

Research Methodology: This research is based on the comparative-analytical method. Character creation methods from Eastern and Western literary examples were compared thematically and aesthetically. The content and essence of the characters were analyzed based on textual, cultural, and historical approaches. The forms of expression of characters were studied based on factors such as metaphorical depiction, symbolism, and psychological analysis. Characters in Eastern literature often carry symbolic and moral content. Here, human life, inner experiences, and spiritual perfection are more connected with religious-philosophical thinking. For example, characters like Layli and Majnun, Khusrav and Shirin, Bahrom and Gulandom in Persian-Tajik literature represent not only symbols of love but also ideas such as striving for divine truth, spiritual purification, and social elevation. Characters created in the works of Alisher Navoi in Uzbek classical literature, such as Farhod, Shirin, Majnun, Beauty, and Intellect, reflect the life experience, moral values, and aesthetic taste of the people. In Eastern poetic thinking, characters are used more for artistic interpretation of the inner world and spiritual-mental state of humans rather than important socio-political issues of society.

In Western literature, the main direction of character creation is related to realism, psychologism, and individualism. Although characters created in Homer's epic works are based on Greek mythology, their actions, thinking, and feelings are filled with human aspects. Later, authors like Dante, Shakespeare, Goethe, Tolstoy, Dostoevsky, and Kafka paid special attention to the inner psychological analysis of characters. In Western literature, characters are more often portrayed as individual characters. They are formed around concepts such as their place in society, social relationships, psychological conflicts, consciousness and unconsciousness, freedom and responsibility. For example, Shakespeare's Hamlet or Tolstoy's Anna Karenina were created as artistic expressions of human dramas. In Eastern literature, characters are more often presented through symbols. Concepts and values are expressed through symbolic signs. Images such as flowers, nightingales, deserts, rivers, and mountains are not just nature scenes, but they represent certain spiritual states, love, loyalty, grief, patience, sacrifice, and other spiritual ideas. In Western literature, characters are interpreted in an analytical style, based on real reality. There, the human person is at the center, and the complex socio-psychological aspects of human life are revealed through literary characters.

Throughout historical development, Eastern and Western literatures have influenced each other. This influence is also reflected in character creation styles. For example, Western novel writing has influenced Eastern literature, while interest in Sufi philosophy and Eastern poetics has increased in the West. In the 20th century, cosmopolitanism, globalism, and cultural dialogue strengthened in the literary process. This led to the integration of various styles in creating literary characters. In contemporary literature, there are many characters that embody national and universal values. In particular, in modern Uzbek prose, characters created in the synthesis of

a person's place in society, nationality, modernism, and postmodernism approaches are emerging based on relevant topics.

Analysis and Results: In Eastern literature, characters are mainly created through symbols, based on spiritual-aesthetic ideas. They often represent moral maturity, inner harmony, and spiritual perfection. In Western literature, characters are created with a realistic and psychological approach. In this literature, characters illuminate complex contradictions between society, personality, consciousness, and environment. According to the analysis results, both literary schools rely on their own methods for character creation, but a harmony of these approaches is observed in contemporary literature. Based on comparative analysis, it can be said that characters in Eastern literature are created more on an ideological-moral approach, while Western literature emphasizes psychological analysis and realism. Although there are commonalities between these two traditions, the main difference is manifested in their aesthetics and authorial position. Eastern literature interprets the character as a symbol carrying a spiritual idea, while in Western literature, the character is seen as a means of artistic analysis of a person's inner world. Such approaches determine the uniqueness of both literary schools. At the same time, a universal character system is forming in contemporary literature through the integration of these approaches.

The uniqueness of character creation methods is related to the national characteristics of literary thinking. Each nation forms its system of characters based on its historical experience, religious-philosophical views, social life, and aesthetic taste. In this system, the character is viewed not just as an artistic personage but as an expression of the nation's thinking, spiritual world, and life philosophy. A comparative approach allows for scientifically studying this diversity, identifying common and different aspects, and understanding the patterns of literary development.

Discussion: The differences in character creation methods are closely related to the aesthetic views, philosophical foundations, and cultural values of each literary school. While characters like Layli and Majnun, Farhod and Shirin, Beauty and Intellect in Eastern literature depict a person's striving for divine truth and spiritual purification, characters like Hamlet and Anna Karenina in Western literature reveal a person's inner contradictions, psychological states, and social problems. Cultural historical processes, literary influences, and inter-civilization relations have caused changes in character creation methods. Cosmopolitanism and global cultural dialogue have further complicated this process. A comparative analysis of character creation methods in Eastern and Western literature serves to identify harmony and differences between these two literary schools, study their mutual influence, and determine their contribution to the development of contemporary literature. From this perspective, it is possible to penetrate the deep layers of literary thinking through character analysis and understand its aesthetic and ideological foundations. This is an important source for conducting scientific research in literary studies.

Conclusion: A comparative analysis of character creation methods in Eastern and Western literatures provides an opportunity to understand the aesthetic, ideological, and cultural foundations of each literary school. In the East, characters more often express spiritual ideas through symbols, while in the West, they appear as artistic interpretations of personal psychological states. In both schools, characters are closely linked with people's thinking, historical experience, and artistic traditions. In contemporary literature, a new system of artistic characters is forming through the synthesis of these two approaches. This research serves to

improve comparative study methods in literary studies and to understand cultural thinking deeply.

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